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The Impact of the Application of Green Marketing Criteria on Marketing Performance

By

**Abdullah Mohammad Hersh
Abdelmo'ti Suleiman Aburoub
Mahmoud Mohammed zyood**

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Dr. Abdullah Mohammad Hersh, Dr. Abdelmo'ti Suleiman Aburoub,
Dr. Mahmoud Mohammed zyood

¹Al Balqa Applied University. Email: Abdullah.hersh@gmail.com

²King Abdulaziz University-KSA. Email: emad75@hotmail.com
King Abd Alaziz university - KSA.

Corresponding Author's Email: Abdullah.hersh@gmail.com

Abstract

Green marketing is one of the most important strategies which business organizations operate in order to gain consumers confidence on one hand, government's confidence and others who are working to protect the environment on the other hand. The survival of organization in the market depends on its commitment to the standards of environmental protection and consumer from the damage that may arise from its work. Therefore, this study aims to identify the impact of the application of green marketing standards on the marketing performance of Rabigh Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh), and in order to achieve this goal, a questionnaire was designed and distributed to the management of Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh) at its all levels (upper, middle and lower) to take their opinions, analysis them and extract the results of the study. The study has reached a conclusion that green marketing is a criteria that has a strong and direct relationship in achieving an effective marketing performance, with the exception of profitability where the relationship was weak. Also, the standard of social responsibility has the greatest impact on the marketing performance of Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh). however, the least one was the standard of service. The study found that the impact of green marketing standards on the marketing performance with the existence of the four variables of organization's culture that became homogeneous and there were no differences in influence between them.

Keywords: Green marketing, marketing performance, the organization's Culture.

1. Introduction

For a period of time, many of those who were interested in marketing activities had believed that focusing on the sales volume standard was a success indicator of the marketing activities which were geared towards building a direct and strong relationship between the company and its customers, and perhaps the increasing of sales volume is what forms all the marketing policies that are used by the company and it represents an evidence for the company's success. On this basis, many of the production and marketing companies have adopted different policies which consist a lot of inequity toward human and harming the environment, depending on the publicity of these ideas and not form the marketing culture for the consumer, as well as the lack of serious legal legislation, which can stand firmly to curb this trend. However, the increasing of environmental problems during the past three decades caused an expansion of the environmental awareness, many problems such as the widening of the ozone hole in the atmosphere, global warming, forest sweeping, as well as acid rain, high levels of air, water pollution, and many of the climatic phenomena, so that prompted many specialists and researchers to search solutions to these environmental phenomena, and one of these trends was the green marketing as a contemporary philosophical which seeks to create a state of suitability between the orientations of the production processes stakeholders and marketing in order to achieve a competitive advantage for projects that seek to apply the contents of green marketing philosophy. So this study comes to verify these environmental trends at the Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh) because it is one of the most productive companies for the environmental pollution factors, which reflects the importance of applying the green marketing standards for it, and the role of its organizational culture in marketing performance that illustrated in increasing profitability and customer satisfaction about it, at the result the positive impression about their work and improving its reputation have a significant role in its survival in the market and work continuation.

2. Study Problem

Green marketing is one of the important and modern strategies which are strengthening the relationship between the organizations on one hand, and between the community and environment protection institutions on the other hand. From this principle, the industrial organizations operating in Saudi Arabia do not provide a minimum of

support for the various environmental efforts. So that clearly affects the organization's realization about social and moral responsibility towards the environment and society, so this study comes to answer the following questions:

- A. Is there a trend from the Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh) to adopt mechanisms for environment and society protection and improve them?
- B. Is there a possibility from Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh) to apply the standards of green marketing to improve its marketing performance or service which is provided to the community?
- C. Is there a role for the organization culture which adopted by Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh) influence its trend to adopt green marketing strategy?

3. Study Objectives

The objectives of study are:

- Identify the role of green marketing standards in achieving an effective marketing performance at the Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh)
- Tounderstand the role of organization culture adopted by Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh), that shown by the organizational culture, organizational values , organizational beliefs, organizational trends, for adoption of the green marketing strategy to improve its marketing performance
- Creating an action plan in order to reach the culture of green marketing, which serves each of the company, the community and the environment.

4. The Importance of study

The importance of the study is illustrated by the following:

- The importance of applying the concept of green marketing as modern concept in Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh)
- The Renewable international attention, through the organization of consumer protection and environmental protection, in order to avoid all kinds of damage whether on the environment or humans.

The green marketing principles and requirements from evidence can be guided by the Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh) to achieve the marketing performance which leads to satisfying its customers, improving its reputation and ultimately increasing its profitability.

The study Model: Figure (1) 5.

Figure 1: The following figure shows the study Model

6. Study Hypotheses

The first Main hypothesis

H1: There is a significant statistical relationship between green marketing criteria in combination (social responsibility, business ethics, environmental damage, services) and marketing performance.

These sub-hypotheses are derived from the first Main hypothesis:

H1a: There is a significant statistical relationship between green marketing criteria in combination (social responsibility, business ethics, environmental damage, services) and between customer satisfaction.

H1b: There is a significant statistical relationship between green marketing criteria in combination (social responsibility, business ethics, environmental damage, services) and between the positive impression.

H1c: There is a significant statistical relationship between green marketing criteria in combination (social responsibility, business ethics, environmental damage, services) and between organization's reputation.

H1d: There is a significant statistical relationship between green marketing criteria in combination (social responsibility, business ethics, environmental damage, services) and between profitability.

The second Main hypothesis

H2: There is a significant statistical effect between green marketing criteria (social responsibility, business ethics, environmental damage, services) and marketing performance.

These sub- hypotheses are derived from the second Main hypothesis:

H2a: There is a significant statistical effect between social responsibility Criterion and marketing performance.

H2b: There is a significant statistical effect between business ethics Criterion and marketing performance.

H2c There is a significant statistical effect between environmental damage Criterion and the marketing performance.

H2d: There is a significant statistical effect between services Criterion and the marketing performance.

The third Main hypothesis

H3: There are significant statistical differences between green marketing criteria in combination and marketing performance, they are attributed to the organization's culture (organizational culture, organizational values, organizational beliefs, Organizational trends)

7. Literature Review

The Concept of Green Marketing

The Green Marketing is a philosophy and organized, integrated marketing thought aims to create a positive impact in the customer preferences which motivates them towards request products that are not harmful to the environment and development.

Their consumption habits in line with it, work to provide integrated marketing mix based on creativity, which leads to achieve the natural environment preservation, consumer's protection and satisfaction, as well as to achieve the goal of profitability for the company in order to survive and continue, so the application of the green marketing concept is based on the modifying use of natural resources and raw materials which is suitable with environment requirements and production processes modification to match the fundamental objectives of the green marketing (Kärnä, 2003). On the other hand, the green marketing is a legitimate child of the social responsibility of marketing because, it includes social and ethical considerations on how to highlight the positive effects of the organization and reducing their negative impact on society, both in the preservation of the environment and its sustainability, or to provide products that are not harmful to the consumers and the environment alike, a lot of marketing scientists and researchers have discussed the concept of green marketing and agreed mostly on the core implications of the green marketing concept, and differences illustrated in formal and verbal drafting of the green marketing concept,(Henion & Kinnear, 1976) both noted that ecosystem marketing is an " interest in all marketing activities that contributed to create an environmental problems that could contribute to finding a cure for these problems .Otherwise, (Peattie, 1995) has pointed to the environmental marketing concept as " the overall management process which is responsible for identifying, anticipating and satisfying the requirements of customers and the community in a profitable manner, taking into account the principle of sustainability but, (Walter, 1993) defines the environmental marketing as "Environmental practices led by environmental supervisors as a proof of the growth and progress of commercial process. (Stanton, et al. 2007)

has pointed to the definition of green marketing as "a set of activities that can cause or ease any kind of transaction which aim to meet or satisfy human needs and requirements without any harm on the natural environment. (Pride & Ferrell, 2009) both has been identifying the green marketing as "the process of development, pricing and promotion of products that do not cause any damage to the natural environment. (Bakri, 2006), describes the green marketing as " an organised and integrated entrance which aims to affect customer's preferences which motivates them to demand products which are not harmful on the environment and modify their consumption habits in the line with it, and work to provide products to satisfy this trend. So that the final outcome is environment preservation, consumer's protection and achievement of the goal of profitability for the company. (Stanton, 2007) has defined it as " Marketing activity relate to a specific organization, aims to create a positive impact or remove a negative one of a particular product on the environment, (Charter & Polonsky, 1999) define it as: " the process of products marketing or promotion which based on their environmental performance are not harmful on the environment.

It is clear that all of these definitions are consistent with each other in their focus on the marketing activities performance within a strong environmental commitment and offering an eco-friendly goods, also to influence the consumer behaviors and their consumption habits in line with this trend, and not inconsistent with the profitable objective for the organization. Thus, we can define green marketing (green marketing) as a translation of the social and ethical responsibility requirements for marketing, which came to light in response to the environmental challenges growing in recent years, this marketing approach comes in sync with the growing global interest in the consumer rights protection and emergence of organized environmental movements (environmentalism) aims to protect the rights of people to live in a clean environment.

The Importance of green marketing

The environmental awareness has been escalated in most countries of the world, so in the result the organizations had to improve it's organizational culture and strategy to preserve the environment in all it s components, (Johri & sahasakmontri, 1988, 266) have pointed that there are many companies which consider the environmental face as a long-term strategy rather than as a way to gain the consumers confidence in the short term, also (Mckenna, 1991,67) said that in order to create a long-term relationship with the customers of organization, the marketing administration must make a linking between the organization capabilities and customer needs, so that making it search for suitable solutions for environmental problems through development of eco-friendly and green products, processes and services, also the organizations working to create income and profit through transactions which agree with social and environmental objectives within its marketing strategy that areenvironmentally committed (Menon, 1997, 54), studies have confirmed that the adoption of green marketing strategy works to reduce the costs and reap the benefits and advantages, and if the company breached its environmental obligations, it will pay additional costs and fines by the law which reduces its competitive ability (Porter & Van der Linde, 1995), Green marketing may achieve many significant benefits and gains for organizations that adopt this concept, the most important are:

A. Improving the organization's reputation: The organization's reputation is considered one of the factors which is adopted by the group who deal with it, such as the owners, clients, suppliers, employees, banks, non-governmental organizations, consumers and government.

The adoption of the green marketing philosophy makes the organization close to its customers, particularly those who have an environmental concern. (Bakri, 2007) sees that the organizations that adopt the green marketing philosophy have a very strong support from the community at all, because of the compatibility between its objectives and gain new customers in the future, (Miles and Cavin, 2000) have pointed that the good reputation of the organization arises as a result of adopting to a set of principles in the implementation of its various activities such as:

- The principle of credibility with investors, clients and suppliers;
- The principle of trust between the organization, all of the employees, clients and the community.
- The principle of dependency
- The principle of environmental, social and financial responsibility

When the Organization applying the green marketing concepts, dealing in high quality products, are using the honest advertising media, and dealing in a socially and environmentally responsible way, it will have a good reputation in the market that help men marketing to make a good exploitation for available marketing opportunities and impact on the behavior of environmentally conscious consumers,that leading to increase the sales and rise in the market value of the shares, thereby maximizing its value and attract investors to invest in it.

B. Achieve the competitive advantage: It is expected that green marketing approach opens new prospects and attractive market opportunities for Organizations which practised it, so that allowing them to adopt the traditional competition, and thus achieve a competitive advantage.

Ottman (1998) has pointed out that green marketing helps to achieve competitive advantage through creating certain environmental values to the customers and then create eco-friendly market segments, thus making it a forerunner organization over its competitors in the environmental term in the market.

C. profits: The use of high -efficiency production methods, which rely on fewer raw materials or recycled ones. Or saving the energy that would achieve cost savings and thus more profits.

D. Increasing market share: In the light of increasing environmental problems, the consumers loyalty to the market brand will decline over time, and consumers will turn to buy eco-friendly products and packaging, so there is an opportunity for organizations which adopt green marketing to increase their market share (Ottman,1998)

E. Achieving safety in the products providing and operations management: The adoption of green marketing by organizations would make it always seek to provide what is the best for the green consumers, focusing on the production of safe and eco-friendly goods, through increasing its productivity operations efficiency, that means a reducing in the damage and environmental pollution levels which is caused by production processes.

F. The sustainability of activities: Through the green marketing, organizations can avoid the legal prosecution and gain the community support, because of the general acceptance of its goals and philosophy, and continue to provide eco-friendly products.

G. Personal motivations: Green marketing offers opportunities and motivations for responsible managers in the organization to follow the modern and effective methods in providing eco-friendly products and this consider as personal contribution to the environment preserving. Also, (Bakri, 2006) added a number of benefits which are resulting from green marketing practices .

H. Satisfying the owner's needs: It is expected that green marketing approach opens up a new horizon and attractive marketing opportunities to those organizations which practice, at sequence achieving a competitive superiority in the market, that lead the organization to gain higher profits as well as gain a good reputation in the community and meet the needs of the owners through achieving safety in the products providing and operations management, focusing on the production of safe and eco-friendly goods, through increasing its productivity operations efficiency, that means reducing in the damage and environmental pollution which is caused by these processes, as well as avoiding the legal prosecution which leads to paying the compensation to the affected people and provoking the associations of environment and consumer protection.

I. Achieving social acceptance for organization: Organization's environmental commitment helps to gain a social support to it, consolidate its relations with current customers and gain new customers in the future.

J. The sustainability of activities: When the green organization avoids the legal prosecution and gains the community support, because of the general acceptance of its goals and philosophy, that makes it able to continue providing eco-friendly products, and supporting its operations and its business activities.

Second: the culture of the organization

(Stadha, 2009) has pointed that the culture of the organization has a great role in judging the behaviors and decisions and identifying the acceptable and non- acceptable ones across various levels within the organization, also it awards the organization its identity, in addition it affects the business performance way by influencing the employees behaviors and actions in line with the popular values and beliefs within the organization (Abdullatif, jwdah.2010, p 12)

One of the definitions of the organization's culture is "a pattern of beliefs and expectations which is shared by members of the organization, and these beliefs and expectations create the criterions and shape the individuals and groups' behavior in the organization (Lok & Crawford, 2003). Also (Alter, 2002: p76) has gone to define the culture of the organization as common understanding about the relationships and practices which determine the behaviors of employees in the organization and the way of achieving works, it is a mixture of written and unwritten promises. (Johns & Saks 2005, p256) has explained that the culture of the organization include a set of values , beliefs and assumptions that are shared between Organization's members, the culture of organization includes the following:

1. Organizational culture: it is a set of values , beliefs, concepts and thinking ways which are shared between management and employees in the organization, may be it is unwritten, but it is a cognitive, and all members involves in its composition (Abu Bakr, 2002, p 406), (Johns & Saks, 2005, p265) has indicated that the organizational culture determines the lifestyle for workers in the organization, and includes the values that describe the life of the organization, so they would be more easily to understood by employees.

2. The organizational values, (Dosari, 2007) has identified the organizational values as the common and agreed rules between the workers in the organization which work to determine the behavior of workers in the work environment, such as respect others, as well as the commitment with organization's regulations and laws, the respect of environment and all its components is considered as a part of organizational values which the organization seeks to be included in the behavior of its employees.

3. Organizational beliefs: They are the shared ideas among the employees in the organization which we determine through their nature of work and social life in the work environment as well as determine how the job is done and divided amongst workers (Qawi, 2003). Also the functional tasks, and the importance of involving employees in decision-making (al-Omian, 2010).

4. Organisational trends: (Jawad, 2010) has pointed that it is the positive or negative response of the individual towards things, events or activities, according to what he learned from the rules and laws which are used by the organization, also (Qaryouti, 2000) has noted that the organisational trends and their role in guiding the individual to act in a certain way comes as a result of his acquisition to them during years of his growth and these trends are influenced by the reference group from his family and friends etc. (Jawad, 2010) has defined it as the individual's response to the surrounding environment whether individuals, groups or materials, and it depends on what he learned from the rules, laws and theories so in the end it forms his trends, whether they are positive or negative.

The marketing performance

The concept of marketing performance

The marketing performance, (Ambler, 2005) has defined it as the level of company's achievement to its objectives which set in the marketing plan, (Gharbaoui,2007) indicates that marketing performance is " the marketing outputs or results, which marketing function seeks to achieve it during a particular period of time, while (Asiggbu, awa, & Ogbonna, 2011) have identified it as " the contribution of the marketing function to achieve the objectives of the organization, also it is the relationship between marketing activities and business performance (Clark & Ambler, 2001).

We can conclude from these definitions that marketing performance reflects the level of organization's success or failure, through its quest to achieve the objectives which are illustrated in continuing and adapting the external environmental changes, the fact that business organizations have begun facing a rapidly environmental change in its resources, size of the demand and intense competition in the market, that making them seek to develop new technologies to enable them to respond to the different variables and achieve their aims, through using an objective and effective marketing performance standards.

8. Test hypotheses of the study

The first Main hypothesis

Table (1) explains the following results:

1. All sub- hypotheses are accepted, as well as the first main hypothesis because the corporal significance of all hypotheses became less than a statistical significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$).
2. There is a significant statistical relationship at the level of ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) between the green marketing criteria (in combination) and marketing performance variables (customer satisfaction, positive impression, the organization's reputation, profitability).
3. On the other hand, through the results of study hypotheses test, a discrepancy in the correlation coefficient values is found between green marketing criteria (in combination) and each variable of marketing performance, and this indicates that there is a discrepancy of green marketing criteria's impact on each of them, and the range of this effect as follows:
 - Strong and there are correlation coefficients: (0.914) (0.953) (0.899) (0.921), for each of the (customer satisfaction, positive impression, reputation of the organization).
 - A weak and there is correlation coefficient (0.415) for the profitability variable.

Table 1: Test relationship between green marketing criteria in combination and marketing performance Variables.

Hypotheses	Marketing Performance Variables	R	R ²	β	F Calculated	Sig.
H1	The variables marketing performance in combination	.841	.116	.023	.264	.009
H1a	Customer satisfaction	.914	.836	.274	3.187	.010
H1b	Positive impression	.921	.848	.357	3.137	.000
H1c	organization's Reputation	.899	.808	.526	3.430	.000
H1d	Profitability	.415	.181	.517	.443	.014

The second Main hypothesis

Table (2) explains that the simple regression test of the study variables has a corporal significance at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), and the value of (F calculated) is (37.336), while (R²) was reached (0.257) that means the impact factors explain (26%) of marketing performance changes in the Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh), and if one unit of green marketing criteria increases, the marketing performance will also increase as a rate of (48.5%), and the value of (T calculated) is (6.271), it is a corporeal at the significance level of ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) so there is a corporeal effect of green marketing criteria on the marketing performance. through these results, we can test the Sub hypotheses which derived from the second main one, and Table (3) explains the results of sub-hypotheses test.

Table (3) explains all the results of simple regression, which represent the relationship between each criterion of Green marketing on one hand and marketing performance on the other hand, have an effect relation, based on the values of F-test which its corporeal significance levels to each of them are less than statistical significance level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$). Social responsibility criterion explains the highest rate (32.3%), while services criterion explains the lowest percentages (10.9 %),that means social responsibility criterion has the most (important effect on marketing performance from other criteria.

Therefore, the final result indicates that the four alternative sub- hypotheses are accepted, which states :There is a significant statistical effect between green marketing criteria (social responsibility, business ethics, environmental damage and services) and marketing performance at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$).

Table 2: The impact of green marketing criteria (in combination) on the marketing performance

Independent variable	F Calculated	DF	R ²	R	Simple linear Regression		
					Sig	T Calculated	β
Green marketing criteria	37.336	1.84	0.257	0.543	0.000	6.271	0.485

The Table 3: Effect of green marketing criteria on the marketing performance

green marketing criteria	F Calculated	R ²	R	DF	Regression coefficient		
					Sig	T Calculated	β
Services	11.524	0.109	0.330	1.84	0.001	3.395	0.272
environmental damage	24.343	0.206	0.454		0.000	4.934	0.356
social responsibility	44.873	0.323	0.568		0.000	6.699	0.369
business ethics	14.925	0.137	0.370		0.000	3.863	0.287

The third Main hypothesis

In order to examine the validity of this hypothesis, (One way *anova) was used to test the effect of study variables. Table (4) explains: There are no significant statistical differences between green marketing criteria in combination and marketing performance, they are attributed to the organization's culture, it has no corporeal significance based on the value of statistical significance (**Sig = 0.301**) and it is bigger than statistical significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), **so that the alternative hypothesis is rejected and the null hypothesis is accepted.** In addition, the results of (Levene) test indicates that there is homogeneity for the effect variance of the green marketing criteria on the marketing performance due to the organization's culture; the following table shows the result.

Table (5) explains that there is homogeneity for the effect variance of the green marketing criteria on the marketing performance due to the variables of organization's culture (organizational culture, organizational values, organizational beliefs, Organizational trends) based on the value of statistical significance (Sig = 0.501), and it is bigger than statistical significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$).

Table 4: (One way anova) test to examine the differences between green marketing criteria (in combination) and marketing performance, they are attributed to the organization's culture

Organization's culture	Source of variation	Sum of squares	DF	Average squares	F	Sig
Green marketing criteria (in combination)	Between groups	0.833	2	0.417	0.693	0.301
	Within the groups	55.899	136	0.601		
	Total	56.732	138			

Table 5: (Levene) test

	Sig	Df2	Df1	Levene
Organization's culture	0.501	136	2	0.348

9. Findings

1. There is a strong correlation between each of the green marketing criteria in combination and marketing performance variables (customer satisfaction, positive impression, the reputation of organization), in Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh).
2. There is a weak correlation between each of the green marketing criteria in combination and marketing performance variable (profitability) in Refining and Petrochemical Company (Petro Rabigh).
3. There is a significant statistical reference between green marketing standards and marketing performance, and the impact of these standards was disparate as follows:
 - a) The standard of social responsibility explains a higher rate than the rest of the criteria which influence on the marketing performance values, it represented (32.3%), and thus the standard of social responsibility has the largest impact on the marketing performance of the other criteria.
 - b) The lowest interpretation percentage was the standard of services; it represented (10.9%).

There are no significant statistical difference for green marketing standards in combination on marketing performance due to the culture of organization (organizational culture, organizational values, organizational beliefs, organizational trends), and also, the impact of green marketing standards on the marketing performance for the four variables of organization's culture is homogeneous.

References

- Abu Bakr M, (2002). The administrative organization in contemporary companies, University House, Cairo.
- Al-Nuaimi MA, (2009). The Contemporary Quality Management, fourth edition, Yazouri for publication, Amman, Jordan
- Al-Dosari JF, (2007). Organizational culture in security organizations and their role in total quality application, Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, University of Naif for Security Sciences, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.
- Al-Omian MS, (2005). The Organizational behavior in business organizations, Wael Press for publication. Amman, Jordan.
- Al-Saeed IM, (2009). Strategic Management, concepts and application areas, Arab office, Egypt.
- Alter S, (2002). Information system: the foundation of e-business , (4nd ed.). Prentice Hall. New Jersey.
- Ambler T, Roberts J, (2005). Beware of the Silver Metric: Marketing Performance Measurement has to be Multidimensional,” Centre for Marketing working paper, No. 05-709.
- Anderson, E. *et al.* (1994) Customer satisfaction, market share, and profitability: Findings from Sweden. *Journal of Marketing* 58 (3) 53-66.
- Armstrong JS, Collopy F, (1996). Competitor orientation: effects of objectives and information on managerial decisions and profitability. *Journal of Marketing Research*. 33. (2):188-199.
- Asiegbu F, Awa O, Akpotu C, Ogbonna B, (2011). Sales force competence development and marketing performance of industrial and domestic products firms in Nigeria, *Far East Journal of Psychology and Business*. Vol. 2, No. 3 pp. 43-59
- Bakri T, (2006). Marketing: contemporary Principles and concepts, Yazori press for publication and distribution, Amman, Jordan. P. 25.
- Bakri T, (2008), marketing strategy, Yazouri press for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
- Bakri T, Al-Nouri, A (2009). Green Marketing, Yazouri Press for publication and distribution, first edition, Amman, Jordan.
- Buxel H. and Wiedmann KP, (2005). Corporate Reputation Management in Germany; Results of an Empirical Study. *Corporate Reputation Review* 8, no. 2: 145-163.
- Carroll AB, (1999). Corporate social responsibility: Evolution of a definitional construct. *Business & Society*, 38(3), 268–295.
- Chandra P, (1997). Financial Management: Theory and Practice.
- Charter M, Polonsky M. (1999). Ed Greener Marketing, Greenleaf Publishing Sheffield: UK.
- Clark BH (1999). Marketing performance measures: history and interrelationships. *Journal of Marketing Management*. 15(8):711-732.
- Clark B, Ambler T, (2001). Marketing Performance Measurements: Evolution of Research and Practice. *International Journal of Business Performance Management*. 3 (2\3\4):231-244
- Clark B, Abela A, Ambler T, (2006). An information processing model of marketing performance measurement. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 14(3): 191–208
- Drucker PF (2000). Management & leadership — Organization of people and work around information, Video, Vol. 3, MTS Publishing, Naperville,
- Fornell C *et al.*, (1996). The American Customer Satisfaction Index: Nature, Purpose and Findings, *Journal of Marketing* 60, no. 4 p.7-18
- Friedman M, (1970). The social responsibility of business is to increase its profits. *New York Times Magazine* (September 13).
- Ghalibi T and Idris W, (2009), Management Strategy "integrated systematically perspective, 2nd edition, Wael press for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, p. 524
- Gharbaoui AA, Azim M, (2007). Contemporary Marketing. University House, Egypt, p. 269.
- Harem H, (2009). Organizational behavior, individuals and groups behavior in business organizations, Al-Hamed for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan
- Henion K, Kinnear T, (1976), A guide to ecological marketing”, in Karl E. Henion and Thomas C. Kinnear (Eds). *Ecological Marketing*. Columbus, Ohio: American Marketing Association
- Iltner C, Larcker D. (2003). Coming up short on nonfinancial performance measurement. *Harvard Business Review*. USA.
- Jawad S (2010), management information systems, Warraq Foundation for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan
- Jawdh M, Abdul L, Abdul L, (2010). The organizational culture and its impact on the job satisfaction of employees, *Damascus University Journal of economic and legal Science*, Volume 26, Issue 3:P120.
- Johns G, Saks AM, (2005). Organizational behavior :understanding and managing life at work, (6 nd ed.) Prentice Hall :.Canada
- Johri LM, Sahasakmontri K, (1998). Green Marketing of Cosmetics and Fdsx\Toiletries in Thailand, *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol. 15, Number 3.
- Kaplan R, Norton D (1996). Linking the balanced scorecard strategy. *California Management Review*. 39 (1).
- Kärnä J, (2003). Environmental Marketing Strategy and its Implementation in Forest Industries, University of Helsinki for public defence in Auditorium, Academic Dissertation.

- Khalil NM, (1998). The competitive advantage in business, Alexandria Center for Book, p. 37
- Kotler P, Armstrong G, (2007). Principles of Marketing. 12th ed., New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Leary MR, Kowalski RM, (1990). Impression management: A literature review and two-component model. *Psychological Bulletin*, 107, 34-47.
- Leary M, Kowalski R, (1990), "Impression management: a literature review and two--component model", *Psychological Bulletin*, Vol.107, No.1, 34—47
- Lok P, Crawford J, (2003), The effect of organizational culture and leadership style on job satisfaction and organizational commitment. University of Technology, Sydney, Australia,.
- Mar,J.,(2003),"Green Marketing ",Prentic-Hall Co.,
- McKenna (1991) 'Marketing is everything', Harvard Business Review, Jan pp.65-84
- Menon A, Menon A, (1997). Enviropreneurial marketing strategy: the emergence of corporate environmentalism as market strategy. *Journal of Marketing* 61, pp. 51–67.
- Miles MP, covin JG, (2000). Environmental Marketing: a source of reputational,competitive and Advantage, *journal of Business Ethics*,vol 23, p 300.
- Miles R, Snow C, (1978). *Organizational strategy, structure and process*. London: McGraw Hill.
- Nouri, AN, (2003). The analyzing of consumer behavior according of green marketing entrance,". Unpublished Dissertation, Management and Economics College, University of Baghdad,
- O'Sullivan D, Abela D, (2007). Marketing performance measurement ability and firm performance, *Journal of Marketing*.71 (2): 79 - 93.
- Ottman, JA, (1998). Green Marketing: Opportunity for Innovation, Lincoln wood: NTC,Business Book, McGraw-Hill., p12.
- Peattie K, (1995). Environmental Marketing Management,Meeting The Green Challenge,London: Pitman,p 28
- Porter ME, (1985). "Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance". New York: The Free Press
- Pride W, Ferrell OC, (2009). Marketing Concepts &Strategies ",2nd ed.,Houghton Mifflin Co.process". Mc Graw-Hill,New York,NY.
- Qaryouti MQ, (2000). Organizational behavior, study of human behavior for individual and Grope in leading organizations, Al -Shroq for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan
- Qaryouti MQ, (2008). The contemporary Theory od Organization and organizing, Wael press, Amman, Jordan.
- Qawi B, (2003). The Organization's culture as an essential entrance for Whole development, *Researcher Journal*, Volume 2 Issue 2, pp. 70-71
- Rajagopal (2008). Measuring brand performance through metrics application. 12 (1): 29-38.
- Rosenfeld PR, Giacalone RA, Riordan CA, (1995). Impression management in organizations: Theory, measurement, and practice. New York: Routledge.
- Schlenker BR, Weingold MF (1992). Interpersonal processes involving impression regulation and management. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 43, 133-168
- Smadi S, (2006). Green marketing: the obstacles in Arab region, The Arab Organization for Administrative Development, the fifth Arab Forum for green marketing, Beirut, Lebanon.
- Smaiziene I, Jucevicius R, (2009). Corporate Reputation :Multidisciplinary Richness and Search for a Relevant Definition, *Inzinerine Ekonomika-Engineering Economics*(2) .
- Sontaite M, Kristensen T, (2009). Aesthetics Based Corporate Reputation Management in the Context of Higher Education, Management Organizations Vadyba, Systematic Research is the Property of Management of Organizations Teminai Tyrima, Vol.51.
- Stadtha A, (2009). The culture of organization as one of influencing factors in decision making process, the international scientific conference, the University of Ammar snowy Baloguat.
- Stanton W et al. (2007). Marketing. Mcgraw-Hill., Inc., NewYork
- Tedeschi JT, Reiss M, (1981). Identities, the phenomenal self, and laboratory research.In J.T.Tedeschi (ed), Impression management theory and social psychological research pp3-22) San Diego, Academic Press
- th ed., Tata McGraw-Hill Delhi.
- Verhoef PC, (2003). Understanding the effect of customer relationship management efforts on customer retention and customer share development. *Journal of Marketing* 67 (4) 30-45.
- Walter C, (1993). Environmental Marketing, McGraw-Hill, Inc,*Business Week* Vol. 12, No. 3
- Wiedmann K, Buxel H, (2005). Corporate Reputation Management in Germany: Results of an Empirical Study, *Corporate Reputation Review*, Vol. 8, No. 2.
- Zeithaml V *et al.* (2006). Services marketing; integrating customer focus across the firm. Singapore: Mc-Graw hill. 4th edition.p,106.

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